

Original Article

INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON SKILL ACQUISITION AMONG BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN ENUGU STATE.

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Abstract

This study sought to ascertain how digital technologies affected the students of Business Education at Enugu State Colleges of Education in terms of online learning. Online learning is a form of learning that requires a high degree of independence and autonomy from students and is blended with traditional face-to-face classroom interaction to form a blended learning model.

The study adopted a survey research design. The population of this study as 33 Business Educators. No sampling was used. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question. The study found that social media influence Online learning among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Enugu State. It also revealed that Multimedia influences online learning among students of Colleges of Education in Enugu state. Based on the findings, it is recommended that Business Educators should have access to the necessary technology tools to ensure proper use of these technologies to improve online learning in Colleges of Education in Enugu State.

Keywords: digital Technologies, Online Learning, Business education, Colleges of education.

Introduction

Digital technology encompasses the tools, processes, and systems used in the creation, storage, management, and transmission of data. A significant component of digital technology is information technology, which involves using computers to process and manage digital data. In today's world, businesses and educational institutions increasingly rely on these technologies to enhance their operations and services. Before the digital age, societal functions—such as education, health, and agriculture—relied heavily on analog systems. Analog technologies refer to older methods, such as transmitting sound over electrified copper lines. With the advent of digital transformation, however,

various sectors have experienced significant behavioral and functional shifts. For instance, digital devices such as mobile phones and projectors have revolutionized communication and teaching methods, making information access and delivery more efficient. This study focuses on the impact of digital technologies on online learning among business education students in colleges of education in Enugu State, Nigeria. The research examines the extent to which these students use digital tools in acquiring and developing new competencies.

Digital technologies include a range of electronic tools, systems, and devices that support data creation, storage, and dissemination. These may include computers, mobile phones, digital media,

online platforms, and learning applications. As defined by researchers like Kumi-Yeboah et al. (2020), digital technologies support teaching and learning by enabling users to find, create, analyze, and present information.

According to Gokçearsan (2017), digital technologies are rooted in numeric code and include everything from personal computers and the Internet to smart devices. Gillow-Wiles and Niess (2015) further noted that these technologies enable automatic data processing and have become integral in education. Examples such as smartphones, online games, and social media platforms highlight the expansive nature of digital tools. The integration of digital technologies in education enhances student engagement and fosters creativity. Students no longer rely solely on pen and paper; instead, they use word processing tools, e-books, tablets, and projectors, which make learning more efficient and interactive.

Digital technologies contribute significantly to online learning by fostering problem-solving, structured thinking, and conceptual understanding. Haleem (2022) emphasized that the use of tablets, simulations, and smart boards makes learning enjoyable and keeps students engaged. One of the most influential advancements is the Internet of Things (IoT), which connects devices and facilitates communication between learners, instructors, and learning resources.

According to Nimfel (2022) & Zakka (2021), incorporating digital tools in education equips students with workforce-relevant skills. Business educators must adopt digital competencies to prepare graduates who can navigate modern digital workplaces. Furthermore, digital technologies contribute to achieving educational goals by making instruction more engaging and aligning with current labor market needs.

Odofin (2022) & Adjin-Tettey (2020) further defined digital technology as a broad term covering computing, communication tools, and devices that

manage data using binary code. This efficiency in data management supports various educational, administrative, and entertainment applications within schools and colleges.

While digital technologies offer significant advantages, they also present several challenges, particularly for youth and students. Akila (2023) pointed out issues such as digital addiction, poor communication skills, and health problems like insomnia, anxiety, and decreased physical activity resulting from extended screen time.

Despite these concerns, digital tools still support higher learning outcomes. According to the Digital Adoption Team (2023), innovations such as remote work, social networking, and mobile applications have reshaped lifestyles and work environments. The Universal Business School (2020) added that technologies like word processing and video editing have democratized content creation, making it accessible to students and educators alike.

Nevertheless, as employers demand more digital skills, students must balance the opportunities and risks of technology. Devaux (2017) highlighted the need for workers to acquire new competencies to remain competitive in an evolving job market.

Social media is a major aspect of digital technology that facilitates interaction, collaboration, and information sharing among students and educators. According to Dollarhide (2023), platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram are widely used for communication, engagement, and educational purposes. Thurairatnam (2021) emphasized the role of social media in professional communication and task execution.

Social networking enables even reserved students to participate in academic discussions and collaborative learning. Beqiri (2014) noted that students rely on platforms like Facebook and email to access information and interact with their institutions. Lim (2013) described tools like mobile applications, conferencing software, and synchronous

communication as critical to learning in digital environments.

Moreover, Web 2.0 and social media tools foster personalized and collaborative learning. Powers (2012) argued that these tools bring learners together, allowing for peer-to-peer knowledge exchange and enhancing engagement. As a result, educators are encouraged to move away from traditional lecture methods and adopt digital and social technologies to meet modern students' expectations.

In summary, digital technologies and online learning have become indispensable in education and development. They offer immense potential for improving learning outcomes but also bring certain challenges that educators and students must navigate. With the right implementation and awareness, digital tools—especially in business education—can transform how students learn, interact, and prepare for the workforce.

Recent studies support the integration of social media in education. Delello, McWhorter, and Camp (2015) found that students view social media platforms like Facebook as beneficial tools in the classroom, helping to bridge communication gaps between students and instructors. Milosevic (2015) emphasized similar findings in Serbia, where Facebook enhanced student-professor interaction and strengthened the educational process. To unlock the full potential of these tools, educators need to understand how and why students use social media, thus enabling effective integration into teaching practices.

Lepi (2012) listed Facebook features such as news feeds, discussion boards, and media-sharing capabilities as valuable for education. Similarly, Beal (2022) defined multimedia as the integrated use of text, graphics, animation, audio, and video via computers to improve communication. Multimedia is widely applied in both business and education to cater to diverse learning styles. By combining

multiple forms of media, educators can design more engaging and effective learning experiences.

Digital technologies provide diverse academic opportunities and help close the digital divide, especially in developing countries. According to Ajayi & Afolabi (2019), digital tools increase engagement, collaboration, and excitement in learning. Devaux (2017) described digital education as a means to reach more learners inclusively, offering flexibility for those in remote locations or with scheduling limitations. Technology has redefined learning as an “anytime, anywhere” process, facilitated by portable devices and online platforms.

Kumi-Yeboah, Kim, Sallar, and Kiramba (2020) reported that digital technologies enhance online learning experiences, promoting academic achievement through consistent interaction with course materials and peers. These technologies foster collaboration, project work, and idea exchange through tools like video conferencing and learning management systems (LMS). Such platforms enable students to engage in knowledge-building through online learning.

Online learning, often referred to as e-learning, digital learning, or distance education, is the delivery of educational content through internet-based platforms. According to Moore, Dickson-Deane, and Galyen (2021), online learning encompasses all forms of electronically supported learning and teaching, with content delivered primarily via the internet. It allows learners to engage with instructional materials, instructors, and peers without being physically present in a traditional classroom.

The importance of online learning has grown significantly over the past two decades, especially with the expansion of global internet access and digital technologies. It offers increased flexibility and accessibility, allowing learners to study at their own pace, location, and schedule. This is particularly beneficial for adult learners, working professionals, and individuals in remote or underserved areas who

might otherwise lack access to formal education (Allen & Seaman, 2017).

Moreover, online learning supports lifelong learning, enabling individuals to continuously upskill and adapt to rapidly changing job markets. It also provides educational institutions with the opportunity to expand their reach and reduce operational costs. Online platforms often include multimedia content, adaptive assessments, and collaborative tools that enhance student engagement and personalize the learning experience (Hrastinski, 2008).

In a rapidly digitizing world, the importance of online learning extends beyond convenience. It plays a crucial role in promoting educational equity and preparing learners for the demands of a knowledge-based global economy. As technology continues to evolve, online education is poised to become an even more integral part of modern education systems.

In Nigeria, Business Education plays a central role in promoting self-reliance and digital literacy. Umeh (2021) emphasized that Business Education programs are designed to equip students with practical skills to support employment and entrepreneurial ventures. Amesi & Allison (2022) described Business Education as a program focused on developing ethical, knowledgeable individuals who can contribute meaningfully to society. Okute (2019) added that it prepares students for both personal and professional success, particularly in digitally-driven environments.

Business Education consists of two components: education for business (vocational) and education about business (consumer awareness). As Musa (2020) referenced from Nigeria's National Policy on Education, Business Education teaches physical and intellectual skills that promote individual and societal development.

In Nigeria's Colleges of Education, Business Education is a core program. Originally designed to train teachers for primary education, these colleges now also prepare teachers for junior secondary

schools due to the phase-out of Grade Two Teacher Colleges (Oga & Okpaga, n.d.). Recognizing the importance of digital skills, the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) has integrated ICT-related courses into the minimum standards for Business Education programs. These courses include computer appreciation, ICT applications, word processing, desktop publishing, and spreadsheets (NCCE, 2012).

Abdulkarim & Onwuchekwa (2020) stressed that to effectively implement these standards, institutions must provide essential resources such as qualified ICT lecturers and modern facilities. These facilities include internet-enabled laboratories, software packages (e.g., Microsoft Suite, SPSS), multimedia tools, and video conferencing devices. Ozuruoke and Abdulkarim (2016) agreed that such investments are necessary to produce graduates who are digitally competent and ready for both teaching and non-teaching roles in today's digital economy.

Statement of the Problem

Digital technologies have undoubtedly had a significant impact on online learning across different educational levels. However, it is still unknown how much of an impact they had on Business Education students, particularly those who attended colleges of education in Enugu State. This study is therefore, aimed at identifying the influence of digital technology on online learning among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Enugu state. Digital technology has affected every facet of human life, from agriculture, business, health care, work places and education is quite overwhelming. It has been useful to the students through its tools that can be used to record lectures, self-study, sourcing for reading material and so many others. The importance of digital technology on online learning among business education students is so much. However, students in colleges of education seem to have a shortage of this technology trend thereby depriving the students the acquisition of these vital skills that will help them to

be gainfully employed on graduation. This situation however, motivated the researcher to determine the influence of digital technology among Business Education students in colleges of education in Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the Influence of digital technologies on online learning among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Enugu state. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- (1) determine the influence of social media on online learning among students of College of Education in Enugu State.
- (2) determine the influence of Multimedia on online learning among the college of Education students in Enugu State.

Research Questions

1. What are the influences of social media on online learning among students of College of education in Enugu State.?
2. What are the influences of Multimedia on online learning among the students of college of education in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female Business Educators in colleges of Education on the influence of social media on online learning among students colleges of Education in Enugu State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female Business Educators in colleges of Education on the influences of Multimedia on online learning among students in college of Education in Enugu State.?

Method

This study adopted a survey research design. According to Tanny (2018), survey research design is a method used in quantitative research where researchers administer a survey to a sample of participants or the entire population to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or characteristics of

the population. Therefore, it is suitable for this study because the researcher sought the opinion of Business Educators on influence of digital technology on online learning among students of Colleges of Education in Enugu state. The area of study is Enugu state. The justification for using Enugu State was because it is a cosmopolitan state. The population for the study comprises 33 Business Educators in public Colleges of Education in Enugu state. The enter population was used. This was because of the manageable nature of the population and as a result, there were no sample and sampling technique since the population was manageable. The researcher made use of questionnaire to elicit the opinion of Business Educators on the influence of digital technologies on online learning among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Enugu State. Instrument of the study consists of part 1 and 2. Part 1 was used to elicit information on the background of the respondents using such variables as gender. While, part two having 2 sections with 12 and 11 respectively. Making it a total of 23 questionnaire items. The instrument has a four- point scales of strongly agree (SA), Agree (A) Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). Three experts validated the instrument, one from Mathematics and Computer and two from Business and Entrepreneurship education. The data collected were analyzed . Mean (X) and standard deviation (SD) were used to answer research questions and t-test were used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The data collected and analysed are presented in tables according to the research questions that guided the study and null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. The data analysed were based on the 31 copies of questionnaire returned.

Research Question 1

What are the influences of social media on online learning among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviation on online learning among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Enugu State?

S/N	The influences of social media on learning among students includes:	Male N= 17 \bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Female N= 14 \bar{X}_2	SD ₂	Overall \bar{X}_G	SD SD	Decision
1	provide students with a platform for learning skills	3.0	0.8	2.9	0.9	2.9	0.8	Agree
		0	7	3	2	7	7	
2	allows students to connect and reconnect with others	3.8	0.3	3.4	1.0	3.6	0.7	Agree
		8	3	3	9	8	9	
3	It covers the barriers of distance	3.1	0.3	3.2	0.4	3.1	0.4	Agree
		2	3	9	7	9	0	
4	It is time consuming	2.2	1.3	1.8	1.2	2.0	1.3	Disagree
		4	9	6	3	6	1	
5	It encourages individual learning	3.8	0.3	3.5	0.7	3.6	0.6	Agree
		2	9	0	6	8	0	
6	It disrupts the sharing of ideas and interests	2.0	0.5	2.0	0.5	2.0	0.5	Disagree
		6	5	0	5	3	5	
7	Increases public relationship	3.1	0.3	2.8	0.8	3.0	0.6	Agree
		2	3	6	6	0	3	
8	It is free to use	2.7	0.6	2.7	0.7	2.7	0.6	Agree
		6	6	1	3	4	8	
9	Builds students to student relationship	2.8	0.6	2.5	0.9	2.7	0.7	Agree
		8	0	7	4	4	7	
10	Helps in building communication	2.4	0.9	2.2	0.9	2.3	0.9	Disagree
		1	4	9	9	5	5	
11	Encourages group learning	3.1	1.2	2.8	1.2	3.0	1.2	Agree
		8	9	6	9	3	8	
12	Reach a large audience at a time	2.9	0.5	2.9	0.6	2.9	0.5	Agree
		4	6	3	3	4	7	
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.9	0.6	2.7	0.8	2.8	0.7	Agree
		5	9	7	7	7	8	

The analysis of data presented in Table 1 above shows that overall mean rating for items 4, 6, and 10 ranging from 2.03 to 2.35 showing disagree. This implies that the respondents disagree on the items as the influences of social media on online learning by students of College of Education in Enugu State. Items 2 and 5 have mean ratings of 3.68 and 3.68 indicating strongly agree. While items 1, 3, 7, 8, 9, 11 and 12 have mean rating ranges from 2.74 to 3.19. This means that the respondents agree to the

items as the mean ratings of male and female business educators on the influences of social media on online learning by students of College of Education in Enugu State. The overall cluster mean of 2.87 further indicates agree. The low standard deviation of 0.78 indicates that the respondents have similar opinion to the items.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators on the

influences of social media on online learning by students of College of Education in Enugu State.

Table 2: Summary of t-test analysis of mean ratings of male and female business educators on the influences of social media on online learning among students of College of Education in Enugu State

Variables	N	T	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	17	1.932	29	.061	2.19748	1.08162	NS
Female	14						

The result of t-test analysis in Table 2 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 29 degree of freedom for the 12 items is 1.932 with a significant value of 0.061. Since the significant value of 0.061 is more than the 0.05 level of significant the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference regarding the items on the mean ratings of male and female business educators

on the influences of social media on online learning among students of College of Education in Enugu State.

Research Question 2

What are the influences of Multimedia on online learning among students of college of Education in Enugu State?

Table 4: Mean ratings and standard deviation on the influences of Multimedia on online learning among students of college of Education in Enugu State

S/N	The influences of Multimedia on online learning among students includes:	Male N=17 \bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Female N= 14 \bar{X}_2	SD ₂	Overall \bar{X}_G	SD _G	Decision
13	It help student to store information	3.06	0.83	3.43	0.51	3.23	0.72	Agree
14	It aids in the transmission of information	3.71	0.69	3.50	1.09	3.61	0.88	Strongly Agree
15	It makes learning easy for the learner	2.88	0.48	3.00	0.68	2.94	0.57	Agree
16	It can help to address the needs of students with varying learning style	3.47	1.01	3.64	0.93	3.55	0.96	Strongly Agree
17	Internet assists students to search for solution in their study	2.88	0.49	2.57	0.85	2.74	0.68	Agree
18	It decreases learning effectiveness	2.29	0.69	2.50	0.76	2.39	0.72	Disagree
19	Reduces training costs	2.76	0.66	2.71	0.73	2.74	0.68	Agree
20	Entertaining and educational	3.06	0.24	2.93	0.47	3.00	0.37	Agree
21	Helps in building communication	3.01	0.04	3.02	0.03	3.02	0.04	Agree
22	help students to retain information better	2.29	0.59	2.07	0.73	2.19	0.65	Disagree
23	Use of video do not allows educators to illustrate complex ideas	2.59	0.87	2.29	0.61	2.45	0.77	Disagree

Cluster Mean/SD	2.91	0.60	2.88	0.67	2.90	0.64	Agree
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The analysis of data presented in Table 2 above shows that overall mean rating for items 18, 21 and 23 are 2.39, 2.19 and 2.45 respectively showing disagree. This implies that the respondents disagree on the items as the influences of Multimedia on online learning among students of college of Education in Enugu State. Items 14 and 16 have mean ratings of 3.61 and 3.55 indicating strongly agree. While items 13, 15, 17, 19, 20, and 21 have mean rating ranges from 2.74 to 3.23. This means that the respondents agree to the items as the mean ratings of male and female business educators on the

influences of Multimedia on online learning among students of college of Education in Enugu State. The overall cluster mean of 2.90 further indicates agree. The low standard deviation of 0.64 shows that the respondent’s opinions do not differ remarkably to the itemized.

Hypothesis 2

A significant difference does not exist between the mean ratings of male and female business educators on the influences of Multimedia on online learning among students of college of Education in Enugu State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of mean ratings of male and female business educators on the influences of Multimedia on online learning among students of college of Education in Enugu State

Variables	N	T	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	17	.387	29	.701	.35714	.92187	NS
Female	14						

The result of t-test analysis in Table 4 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 29 degree of freedom for the items is 0.387 with a significant value of 0.701. As the significant value of 0.701 is more than the 0.05 level of significant the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean ratings of male and female business educators on the influences of Multimedia on online learning among students of college of Education in Enugu State.

Discussion of findings

Table one, research question one showed that some of the influences of social media on online learning among Business Education students in Colleges of Education in Enugu state are that they allow students to connect and reconnect with other and also encourage individual learning. The findings is similar to that of Ibitoye and Eze (2019), which identified the influence of social media on Business Education students’ academic performance to include: quick access to e-resources for higher

academic attainment, sharing relevant academic information to peers for higher performance, helping students to have advanced retention of learning. In hypothesis one, table two, there was no significant difference regarding the items on the mean ratings of male and female business educators on the influence of social media on online learning among students of College of Education in Enugu state. The finding agreed with the view of Okoli and Idele (2015) who reported that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of Business Education students on the use of social media as a result of gender.

Some of the influences of multimedia on online learning among Business Education students in College of Education in Enugu state, as shown in Table four, question Two are that they aids in the transmission of information and can help to address the needs of students with varying learning style. This findings is in line with that of Eze, Olumoko and Obi (2020) which revealed that students taught with multimedia instructional strategy have better

academic achievement than the students taught with the conventional teaching method (demonstration) and that the multimedia teaching strategy enhanced the students' acquisition of skill and knowledge. In hypothesis two, table four, a significant difference does not exist between the mean ratings of male and female business Educators on the influences of multimedia on online learning by the students of College of Education in Enugu state. This findings in consistent with the finding of Igwu and Chima-Uduma (2021) that there is no significant difference in teachers' attitude towards the use of multimedia resources and students' academic performance in Business studies in Ekiti state Junior Secondary School.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that there are numerous benefits of digital

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technology on online learning among Business Education students. Some of these influences are from the social medial network. Additionally, multimedia also influences students' ability in online learning in colleges of Education in Enugu state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Business Educators should be exposed to online learning
2. Business Education students should make positive use of multimedia in learning those skills that they need for their profession
3. Government should make use of multimedia and social medial in classroom learning compulsory
4. There should be regular conferences workshops, on the use of digital technologies for effective delivery

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